

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF INTERNET ADDICTION AMONG STUDENTS

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Annotation: We live in an era where the value of high technology is very high. The Internet has become an integral part of our lives. He absolutely conquered all spheres of life. For now, you cannot imagine any mobile device or computer without the Internet. Sometimes you will be surprised at how people lived without them a few years ago and how they became accustomed to it for a short time. The relevance of the topic of this article is that social networks are becoming more and more. To date, they have mastered all the free time of youth and children. In this article, opinions and comments are made about the psychological state of internet dependence among students and young people.

Keywords: Internet, youth, students, psychology, social networks, dependence on Internet, wasted time.

Some scientists seriously deal with the problem of dependence on the Internet and, in particular, dependence on social networks. Every day millions of people spend their free time on the Internet: to search for a job, to get acquainted with new people, to communicate with friends, colleagues, to themselves the necessary information search, to share their knowledge with others and to receive new ones. Now you rarely see young people watching the news. Many have become accustomed to the fact that any information they need can be found on the Internet, and for this they do not need to make a lot of effort. For example, you do not need to go to the library and sort the literature. You can sit at home at the computer with a cup tea, write down what you need in the search field, and the Internet will give you thousands of results. The fact of internet dependence also says that more than half of young people need to access the website at least once a day, and almost a quarter of adolescents access social networks several times a day (from the report).

A person escapes from his problems and goes directly to social networks, where he can forget about it and think of a new life, a new name, "get rid of". Man begins to perceive his "ideal world" as part of reality and does not see the boundaries between them. A person creates his own new image, having loaded himself with qualities that he may not have in life at all. For example, a humble, self-absorbed person in a social network can manifest himself as a friendly, open person. In the Virtual world, a person can show himself as a self-sufficient person who does not need anything, he can meet his spouse, who, as he seems to himself, can be very far away from him. Often, this "virtual image" has nothing to do with the person himself who is looking for what is missing in real life in social networks, so this "ideal life" will be more expensive for him than real.

Many young people cannot do without virtual communication, completely forgetting about communication in real life. Often people can see such a picture on their phones without stopping, for example, in public places, on the street, even when they meet with friends. Over time, a certain reflex develops, a person begins to constantly check his mail in the hope that someone will write to him or visit his page. A person begins to get attached to it. For him it will be important not only to show how he lives, but also to see how others live. Now it's not just for a memorable album, where you can save the important moments of your youth life, but also to place them all on the social network, and then start taking pictures to see who your photos really like and read the reviews of friends and acquaintances. Acquaintances or friends post photos from the wedding, graduation, travel, curiosity begins to prevail, no one wants to miss interesting news, learn something new from the life of friends. Having browsed the photos one by one, one page, the second, the third sheet, the person forgets about the time.

Today there are such "loyal" users who sit Day and night in social networks. In the morning at work or at school, they first go to check their mail, sometimes they spend more time than in the main business. When going home or to work, in the queue, when eating, they use a phone or, for example, a tablet to access social networks. In the evening, returning home, they again sit at the computer, and in the morning everything starts anew. It is worth noting that such people are very fond of lighting their whole life in social networks, that is, with the help of statuses. Statuses change not only according to the type of activity, for example, "eating", "sleeping", "going to work", but also depend on the emotional experiences of this person. The human condition described above is partly reminiscent of dependence on alcohol or, for example, on drugs, from which we can say that dependence on social networks is a disease of young people.

Being constantly on social networks is not the best activity for our brain. This cannot be called some kind of full-fledged mental labor. A person spends his free time simply in vain, instead of this, for example, it is possible to read a book or take a walk with friends. When looking at the news tape of friends or their photos, a person does it quickly and does not think about the incoming data flow. Also, putting information about yourself, for example, a mobile phone number, age, address, personal photos on a public display, a person can fall into the trap of fraudsters. Intruders can disrupt your account and get the necessary information from your correspondence with your parents, friends or acquaintances. Despite all the negative aspects of being in social networks, there are also pros. But first of all, it is necessary to know when to stop and use it wisely. In social networks, there is nothing bad about meeting and getting acquainted with new people, you can find similar people and talk on common topics, find relatives, listen to music or watch movies. Communication on the internet can increase a person's self-esteem and importance. The main thing is not to forget that this is just a secondary connection, the main thing is communication in real life. The possibilities of the Internet are almost endless, the only thing that the global network can never replace is the pleasure of live communication, the pleasure of letters written with the hands of a friend or a loved one, and sitting in front of other people. Flashing screen you can never go out on a picnic with your friends in real life. This, of course, is a big disadvantage of the network, but at the same time it is a big advantage, because you cannot go to virtual reality forever, after all, we are not machines, we are living people. In conclusion, it should be noted that social networks occupy more time of youth, they replace real communication and hobbies.

In conclusion. Despite the fact that they have positive sides, it should be noted that social networks often have a bad effect on the learning and learning process itself, but there are exceptions. Therefore, you need to control the time spent on the internet, it is important to know the limit and not to cross it, otherwise it will turn out against you. I think many will agree with me, there is a lot of information on the Internet, especially for the younger generation, which cannot be read and even seen! Children stop reading books, the circle of communication of adolescents is reduced: they are limited to virtual communication in chat and forums, aggressiveness among young people is growing rapidly, this is due to excessive and sometimes painful enthusiasm for computer games. All this leads to a gradual degradation of the individual.

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